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Applications of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to enhance Sustainable Phytoextraction of Lead from Polluted Soil.

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Abstract:

Soil surface containment of lead (Pb) is widely recognized. Phytoremediation, which involves a number of chemical reactions and cost analysis, has proven to be the most effective approach to recover lead from soil in the previous few decades. This paper compares two modeling approaches, artificial neural networks (ANNs) with the genetic algorithm (GA) and response surface methodology (RSM), with the goal of modeling and optimizing Pb extraction from the contaminated soil via *Pelargonium hortorum*. The Pb tolerance of bacterial strains (NCCP 1844, 1848, 1857, and 1862) was assessed in vitro essays, and then bacteria and citric acid were co-applied on a Pb hyperaccumulator (*Pelargonium hortorum* L.) on Murashige and Skoog (MS) agar medium to ascertain the significance of the suggested solution. After that, *Pelargonium hortorum* L. was used in a pot culture experiment to maximize Pb extraction competency from Pb-spiked (0 mg kg⁻¹, 500 mg kg⁻¹, 1000 mg kg⁻¹, and 1500 mg kg⁻¹) soil. Citric acid (5 and 10 mmol L⁻¹) and *Microbacterium paraoxydans* (1 and 1.5 OD) were added to the mixture. Plants were taken out at 30, 60, and 90-day intervals, and their dry biomass and Pb uptake properties were examined. After using 500 mg kg⁻¹ soil Pb for 60 days, the highest Pb extraction efficiency of 86.0% was attained. Moreover, RSM was used to simulate Pb extraction from the soil. It was based on the Box-Behnken design (BBD) and the ANN-based Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm (LMA). The RSM and LMA projected values were close to 36.0% and 86.05%, respectively, indicating their relevance. The thorough analysis of these results supported the ANN's efficiency, accuracy, and dependability during the optimization process. Therefore, in addition to being potentially economical and environmentally benign, experimental results demonstrated that ANN is an accurate technique to optimize an integrated phytoremediation system for sustained Pb removal.

Keywords—; Index terms: soil contamination; citric acid; bacteria; ANN; RSM

Introduction:

Lead and other heavy metals detected at the soil's surface are determined to be extremely significant for environmental health. Pb is the second most hazardous material according to the "Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry" [1], and it is also on the top priority list of the US Environmental Protection Agency. Its carcinogenicity, lack of biodegradability, poor mobility, and long-lasting presence in soil make it a constant hazard to human life [2, 3]. While its naturally occurring content in soil ranges from 50 to 500 mg kg⁻¹ [4], human activities such as burning fossil fuels, recycling lead-acid batteries, using leaded paints, and vehicle emissions directly contribute to an increased concentration.

Lead has no biological purpose in the growth and development of plants. Instead, because of its elevated concentration, significant biogeochemical cycles become dysfunctional, which in turn disrupts the toxifying microbial community's and soil's enzymatic activities' ability to mineralize nutrients [5]. Lead (Pb) has been linked to neurological, hematological, reproductive, and kidney diseases in humans, but it also produces oxidative stress in plants and adversely affects their morphological, physiological, and biochemical processes [6]. As a result, cleaning up Pb-contaminated soil must be given top attention. Various physical and chemical procedures are part of the classic cleanup strategies.

Unfortunately, not all of these techniques extract Pb entirely. Rather, they only modify its chemical form or move it from one medium to another [7]. In this context, research on phytoremediation, which uses Pb hyperaccumulator plants like *P. hirtorum*, *Phyllostachys pubescens*, and *Iris halopilla*, offers sustainable and eco-friendly methods to permanently remove Pb from soil [8, 9]. Different plant-growth-promoting (PGP) bacteria, including *M. paraoxydans* and *Pseudomonas* (sp), as well as organic chelates, including ethylene diaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), ethylene-hydroxy ethylene diaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA), ethylene diaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA), nitrilotriacetate (NTA), citric acid, and ethylene diaminedisuccinate.

(EDDS), have also been used in conjunction with plants to increase the efficacy of phytoremediation [10–12].

Fig. 1 Layout of study. (I) Selection of Pb-tolerant bacterial strains on LB agar supplemented with different concentration of Pb (a), and effect of *M. paraoxydante* (1.5 OD) and citric acid (10 mmol L⁻¹) on *P. hortorum* germination under Pb stress (40 mg L⁻¹) (b). (II) Pot culture experiment with selected doses of bacteria and citric acid. (III) Feed-forward back-propagation neural network architecture along with four considered parameters (a), and RSM model based on BBD design (b), respectively.

However, research into sustainable solutions—such as those based on artificial intelligence for safe, affordable, and timely methods for the effective phytoremediation of Pb—is still necessary in order to meet the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 6, 12, and 15. Important prediction and optimization techniques that are based on mathematical, computational, statistical, and artificial models—like ANN, RSM, and GA—have been used in a lot of scientific studies lately [13–16].

RSM has been utilized to optimize the removal condition, and the ANN model may be used to forecast the remediation of Pb using GA. Additionally, these models can yield an accurate result and are less complex and expensive. This study's main objectives were to maximize the effectiveness of Pb phytoextraction by optimizing the dose of citric acid and Pb-resistant bacteria, as well as to optimize the integrated phytoremediation system for Pb extraction utilizing RSM, ANN, and GA models.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Figure 1 displays the experimental design's flow chart. In a nutshell, the current investigation was carried out in three stages. The initial phase involved conducting laboratory-based experiments to determine the concentration of citric acid, the dose of Pb for *P. hortorum*, and the selection of Pb-resistant bacteria. To boost Pb phytoextraction efficiency of *P. hortorum*, a pot culture experiment was conducted in the second step, whereby specific bacteria and citric acid were added. The final phase involved optimizing the improved operating conditions of the Pb phytoremediation system using the experimental data and ANN and GA models.

Selection of Pb and Citric Acid Tolerant Bacterial Strains:

In a Luria-Bertani (LB) medium, the growth characteristics of bacterial strains preisolated by [8] were observed in response to a broad range of Pb (0–800 mg L⁻¹) and citric acid (CA) (0–10 mmol L⁻¹). Through the determination of the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) against C₆H₈O₇ and PbCl₂ on LB agar and broth, the tolerance of the bacteria to Pb and citric acid was examined. In short, 200 µL of the bacterial strain was added to LB broth medium, which was further treated with Pb and CA. The bacteria were cultured in a shaker incubator set to 200 rpm and 28 °C. By using an ultraviolet–visible spectrophotometer (Specord 200 plus) to measure the culture's optical density (OD) at 600 nm at regular intervals (2–36 h), the growth characteristics of the strains were examined. The division of the dry biomass of bacteria obtained from the treatment group in a controlled environment following a 24-hour incubation period was used to calculate the tolerance index of the bacterial strains against CA and Pb. Additionally, the cross-tolerance between copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), cadmium (Cd), and zinc (Zn) was also documented. *M. paraoxydans* was identified as the bacterial strain that had the greatest resistance to both Pb and citric acid, and as a result. The laboratory-scale *in vitro* tests were conducted to observe the effects of Pb, citric acid, and *M. paraoxydans* on seed germination and seed vigor index. First, 1/2 Murashige and Skoog (MS) agar medium supplements were made in Petri plates with varying Pb concentrations (0, 10, 20, 30 & 40 mg L⁻¹). Using a glass spreader, 200 µL

of the bacterial inoculum (1.5 OD) suspension and 10 mmol L⁻¹ of the citric acid solution were applied to the agar as treatments.

The Awan Garden Center, F7 markaz Islamabad provided the *P. hortorum* L. seeds, which were soaked in 70% ethanol for 30 minutes and then in 10% NaClO for another 30 minutes to disinfect them. Following a thorough cleaning with sterile distilled water, the seeds were cultured on MS agar Petri plates that had been prepared with Pb and treated with *M. paraoxydans* and citric acid. After that, petri plates were incubated in the dark at 25C for 7 days. Equations (1) and (2) were used to track physiological data, including SVI, germination, and seedling root/shoot length, on Petri plates taken out of the incubator after a week [12–13].

$$GE (\%) = \frac{\text{No. of germinated seeds}}{\text{Total/No. of seeds}} \times 10 \quad (1)$$

$$SVI = L \times GE \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, L stands for mean length and GE for percentage of seeds that germinate.

Soil Characterization and Preparation

A sample of uncontaminated soil was taken from the National University of Science and Technology's nursery in Islamabad, and its physicochemical properties were examined. The Supplementary Data (see Supplementary Table S1) displays the properties of the soil utilized in the experiment. The experimental soil was found to be a clay loam with a pH of 7.63% and 0.83% organic content. Wet digestion was used to confirm the Pb concentration in the spiked soils, and an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) was used to measure the Pb concentration. Pb concentrations in spiked soil of 500, 1000, and 1500 mg kg⁻¹ soil Pb treatments were found to be 469, 935, and 1445 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. This suggests a metal recovery of 93.1% [4,5].

Optimizing Pb Removal from Soil Using Prediction Models

Response Surface Methodology

The response surface method (RSM) belongs to the class of the statistical methods and is very efficient from a computational, mathematical and cost-effective point of view. Here, it is used to evaluate the impact of multiple independent variables of chemical processes and the responses of the experiments. For our work, it is sufficient to assess the effects of each and every variable separately or combined with other groups of variables. The approach supports fitting the model, and it is evaluating the problems by using optimizing process parameters. This non-linear multivariate model regulates experimental conditions and the design to achieve the system's best and most reliable response performance, which results in optimal results. Furthermore, it offers a mathematical model that is most compatible with laboratory analytical findings [20]. RSM based on BBD is applied to optimize the experimental conditions.

Box–Behnken Design and Data Analysis:

The solution PH, ionic strength, dispersion solvent, and soil extraction volume were among the factors that were optimized using the BBD approach. The lead removal effectiveness of *P. hortorum* L. from the contaminated soil by citric acid and *M. paraoxydans* (Table 1 and Table S2) was utilized as the input for a two-leveled BBD with four parameters. Based on the individual results of the initial single- factor tests, the independent variables and their

position values were generated. Additionally, the dependent response variable, yield (Y), is assumed to be the Pb removal efficiency. Separately positioned at the coded values (-1, 0, +1) are the independent variables. The intercept, squared terms of the product of two factors, and a linear analysis are all components of the BBD technique. Equation (3) expresses the correlation between the independent variables and the response as a quadratic model.

$$Y = b_1 + b_2A + b_3B + b_4C + b_5D + b_{13}AB + b_{14}AC + b_{15}AD + b_{23}BC + b_{24}BD + b_{25}CD + b_{7A}A^2 + b_{17}B^2 + b_{27}C^2$$

Artificial Neural Networks Modeling:

An ANN was employed, per [2,3], in order to ascertain the non-linear relations between the variables. To model the ANN, we employed the MATLAB Neural Network Toolbox in version 2020a. While there are many neural network variations available here for diverse applications, the "Feed- Forward Back Propagation Neural Network" (FFBPNN) is the most widely utilized network in the environmental sciences sector. There are several inputs connected to a few outputs in this neural network variation. The network specifically consists of hidden and output layers in addition to several inputs. There were a specific number of neurons in each layer, with the number of neurons in the buried layers being especially significant for response computation. Following data cleaning, 243 numbers from laboratory data are extracted using an excel file that contains four independent variables (Pb Concentration, M. paraoxydane, Citric Acid, Days), and one dependent variable (Pb extraction). This process trains the network. For the purpose of computing the Pb Phytoremediation (the application of higher plants for the economical, environmentally beneficial restoration of soil by harmful metals) model, a three layered neural network architecture was built. Figure 1 displays both the ANN model and the FFBPNN method. Moreover, the "Levenberg–Marquardt back propagation" (LM) approach is used to train the ANN. Newton's approach is approximated by LM [4]. The early stopping strategy was applied in this work by randomly dividing the input dataset into three portions: test, validation, and training sets, with percentages of 15%, 70%, and 15%, respectively. Subsequently, the training dataset was used in order to evaluate the network weights and bias. After then, the training process—which involves adapting through learning—is carried out using the computed errors. The training was halted to allow for appropriate repairs as soon as the computed error at the validation point began to rise once more for a specific amount of duplications.

Genetic Algorithm (GA) with ANN & RSM Comparison:

An optimization heuristic is a GA work. It uses a fitness (objective) function and its limitations to determine the best solution from the possible solution area [5,6]. There are two main paths a GA can take: either optimizing single goal functions or optimizing multi-objective functions.

A singular goal is optimized when a single objective function is optimized, and the result is a unique solution that may be maximal or minimal. A GA uses the three main genetic operations—selection, mutation, and crossover—as its foundation. The first stage in using a GA to produce findings that are feasible is to ascertain the population size, which can be chosen at random in accordance with [7]. If accessible, specialist knowledge can also be used

as an alternative. Calling the goal function verifies each solution candidate in the population. As parents raising the future generation, those candidate solutions in the population with the highest fitness value are selected. The progeny produced by these parents subsequently contribute to the expanding population. In order to do this.

We used a GA to identify the ideal circumstances for Pb removal because our focus is on artificial intelligence-based methodologies for modeling and optimization of Pb removal. This calls for the application of the previously described artificial intelligence models (i.e., RSM and ANN) in a phytoremediation method. The program utilized for this is called Simulink® (MATLAB 2020a). For both the RSM and ANN techniques, the following criteria were established in order to characterize the fitness functions:

1. Fitness function = $1/4$ Min (removal rates from the RSM equation)
2. Fitness Function = $1/4$ Max (removal rates from the RSM equation – $1 \times$ RSM's equation)
3. Fitness function = $1/4$ Min (removal rates from the ANN equation)
4. Fitness Function = $1/4$ Max (removal rates from the ANN equation – $1 \times$ RSM's equation)

We assessed the optimal and worst circumstances for elimination and removal rate using the aforementioned four equations.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Tolerance of Bacteria against Pb and Citric Acid

The ability of several bacterial strains (NCCP-1848, NCCP-1857, NCCP-1862, and NCCP-1844) to withstand Pb and citric acid concentrations was investigated after they were pre-isolated by Manzoor et al. [8]. *M. paraoxydans* (NCCP-1848) exhibited the most significant dry biomass production and tolerance index towards Pb and citric acid, according to the data (see Table 2 as well as Figures 1 and 3). *M. paraoxydans*'s Pb tolerance has already been extensively documented. [8] The generation of organic acids (succinic and acetic acids), as revealed by the metabolic profiling of *M. paraoxydans*, led to a decrease in the medium's pH values and an improvement in the fermentation process of coffee beans. The synthesis of siderophores and indole acetic acid by *M. paraoxydans* has also been reported by Manzoor et al., 2019 [8]. This suggests that bacteria may survive and thrive in low pH environments, which may be brought on by the addition of citric acid. *M. paraoxydans* was chosen for more research as a result.

Figure 3 shows the growth curves of various bacterial strains at different time periods in LB media (a), 1000 mg L⁻¹ Pb (b), and 10 mM citric acid (c).

Predicting Pb Removal Using RSM

In order to forecast the Pb removal using the RSM technique, we ran trials. Using the regression approach, the RSM findings were fitted to a non-linear quadratic equation. Figure 1 shows how the ANN and RSM models' evaluation of the data and prediction outcomes were done. Equation (6) was generated by first choosing and removing the variables that had a non-significant component ($p > 0.05$).

$$Y = 86.04 - 1.5 * A + 10 * B + 60.0 * C + 500 * D - 2.0 * A * C - 1.5 * B * C + 36.04 * A^2 \quad (6)$$

Impact of using *M. paroxydans* and citric acid on Pb uptake (b) and plant biomass (g) in *P. hortorum* (after 90) exposed to varying soil Pb concentrations (0, 500, 1000, and 1500 mg kg⁻¹). At $p < 0.05$, different letters denote a significant difference. In a similar vein, at 1500 mg kg⁻¹ soil Pb content, *P. hortorum* L. showed 130% Pb uptake when citric acid was used, as opposed to the control plant that did not receive citric acid. The application of *M. paroxydans* and citric acid together has a noteworthy ($p < 0.05$) and cooperative impact on Pb uptake (4.8-folds). This effect can be ascribed to enhanced plant biomass and Pb chelation by reducing soil pH, producing IAA siderophores [8], and facilitating metal chelation. Using two factors—*M. paroxydans* and Pb concentration—the surface plots were built as factorial experiments using the BBD approach. The variables were treated and controlled

using a three replicate plot design. ANOVA was used to determine significant differences between the laboratory and anticipated means and results. Using Minitab software, the least significant test design (LSD) was carried out at $p < 0.05$. For the purpose of estimating a reasonable quantity of lead, experimental variables were provided as the data input into the neural network. The test dataset and training verification data for the ANN, which generates the best predictions, are shown in Figure 1. Additionally, measures like mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), regression coefficient (R^2), and standard error (SE) were used to attain statistical performance. In the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm, R has a value between 0 and 1. The potential of the specific spots is estimated by the LM plot. This algorithm determines the values of MSE and MAE with test data of R and the best R 's for all datasets in the design of the experiment encompassing the influence.

Conclusions:

An ANN modeling approach was established in this work. There are various advantages over the reference solutions, chief among them being the efficiency, simplicity, and black box modeling character of this approach. For simulating complicated system behavior, such waste water treatment operations, this indicates that the technique is currently the best option. The ANN has been demonstrated to be a suited and precise method for predictions in almost all experiments. The lab experiment data used to create the ANN model in this paper. To investigate the lead removal from contaminated soil, an RSM-based BBD approach has been employed. This is accomplished in the first stage by washing. For the procedure, we looked at two biodegradable chelates: M. paraoxydance and citric acid. Based on the results of the initial single factor tests, the independent variables and their position values were developed. With the exception of Pb efficiency, every parameter that was chosen had a beneficial impact on the process. All Pb concentration and time interaction effects are non-significant ($p < 0.05$). The response prediction's second-order regression equation has the highest level of accuracy. R^2 is greater than 0.9033. The goal of this study was to characterize, illustrate, and simplify the Pb elimination process of certain blessing bacteria that were found in different agricultural soil testing. The discovery of a novel, potent strain is therefore noteworthy. In conclusion, two distinct approaches RSM and ANN are used in the modeling strategy that is being discussed. Our sample tests revealed that the ANN approach displayed the best-fit findings differently when taking the LM algorithm into account.

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